

VISUALIZING NEW INDIA: TAGORE'S VISION AND LEGACY IN NATIONAL EDUCATION MOVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Rabindranath Tagore was more inclined to prioritize the socio-economic and educational changes especially of the rural folks. He stressed on social and educational reforms. During the Swadeshi movement in Bengal, Tagore played a valuable role and took the leadership of the mass movement against British imperialism. He became critical about imperialistic and materialistic attitude of the European nations. He was the first to propose the concept of non-cooperation. Tagore in his essay University Bill (1904) strongly criticized the Lord Curzon's Higher Education Bill. Rabindranath was included as a member constituted for drawing up a provisional scheme of National Council of Education. In the inaugural ceremony of the Bengal National College and School, Rabindranath was present reconciling his differences of opinions with most of the members of National Council of Education.

Keywords: National Education Movement, National Education Council, Swadeshi movement, Vernacular education.

INTRODUCTION

Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) was a poet educationist and a humanist philosopher. He had a nationalistic ideology which he received from his father Maharshi Devendranath Tagore (1817-1905), his elder brother Jotirindranath Tagore (1849- 1925). Rabindranath imbibed the concept of self-help and self-reliance from the days of Hindumela. He was also exposed to secret revolutionary society established by Jyotirindranath and Rajnarayan Bose (1826-1899). Dwijendranath Tagore (1840-1926), eldest brother of Rabindranath, was serving as its secretary for several years. He also composed patriotic and devotional songs for the Hindumela. Another brother Satyendranath Tagore (1842-1923), the 1st Indian ICS, also played a significant role in the Hindumela. Rabindranath was greatly inspired by the Brahma Samaj and hence he later produced many literary works that instilled a feeling of nationalism amongst the masses. During his lifetime, he wrote more than two thousand songs. His compositions were adopted as the national anthems for India (*Jana Gana Mana*) and Bangladesh (*Amar Sonar Bangla*). He was more inclined to prioritize the social and educational changes especially of the rural folks. He stressed on social and more on educational reforms and wanted to spread vernacular schools throughout Bengal as English education, according to him, could never reach to the Indian mass. Apparently Tagore wanted vernacular education with mother tongue as the medium of instruction to be established everywhere in the country for mass education. Tagore earnestly reiterated what Pandit Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820-1891) said about fifty years ago with respect to mass education through

mother tongue. Tagore wanted an education that was in touch with all strata of life: economic, intellectual, aesthetic, social and spiritual.

OBJECTIVES

- To study Tagore's concept of education inspired by ancient Vedic literature.
- To discuss the major issues addressed by Tagore in his philosophy of education.
- To understand the impact of Tagore in national education during Swadeshi Movement.
- To understand Tagore's vision of nationalism in the context of national education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Why was Tagore interested in gurukul system of education?
- What are the major issues addressed by Tagore in his philosophy of education?
- What was the role of Tagore in national education movement during Swadeshi agitation?
- What was Tagore's vision of nationalism in the context of national education?

METHODOLOGY

The present study related to 'national education' belongs to the area of historical as well as philosophical research. It is in particular a case study of Tagore's impact on national college and national education during the swadeshi days (1903-1908). All data are therefore taken from written records and printed sources.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

R 1: Why was Tagore interested in gurukul system of education?

Tagore visualized a system of education which would be based on the national tradition and established a school known as "Brahmacharya Asram" at Santiniketan near Bolpur in the district of Birbhum in 1901. The school was modelled along the lines of classical gurukul system of ancient India called 'Tapabana' from which emerged the great literary, philosophical and spiritual classics like Vedas and Upanishads. Tagore gathered the Tapabana ideas from the epic writings of Kalidasa.

R 2 : What are the major issues addressed by Tagore in his philosophy of education?

In his educational philosophy, Tagore wanted a true synthesis of the East and West. He strongly advocated the study of European literature, and science and technology. To him these were essential studies, but he proclaimed that the literature and science of Europe should be blended with our national consciousness based on the century-old-literary, cultural spiritual and moral heritage of India. He believed and advocated that the vernacular should be the medium in every stage of education and all official activities and proceedings of the country.

R 3 : What was the role of Tagore in national education movement during Swadeshi agitation?

During the period of swadeshi movement in Bengal (1902- 1908) Tagore played a valuable role and took the leadership of the struggle of mass against British Imperialism. The University Bill of Lord Curzon had the imperialistic design of curtailing higher education in the country in the name of improvement of quality. Tagore in his essay University Bill (1904) strongly criticized this.

Anti-partition (1905) upsurge swept Bengal. Slogans of *swaraj* (self-rule), *swadeshi* (use of indigenous goods), *boycott* (of all foreign goods and manufactures) and *jatiyashiksha* (national education) emerged vigorously during the anti-partition campaign. Rabindranath worked for the emotional integration of the Bengalis. Besides essays, pamphlets and speeches, he composed innumerable *swadeshi* (national) songs – to rouse the consciousness of the Bengalis against British domination and to instill in them a sense of fearlessness and self-reliance. Many of these songs, he sang himself in the anti-partition meetings in the street agitations or in other public gatherings.

The ‘Carlyle Circular’ was published in the *Statesman* on October 22, 1905. The circular prohibited students’ participation in political rallies, *swadeshi* picketing and meetings and ordered rigorous disciplinary actions against the students. The heads of the schools and colleges were warned by the magistrates that if their students were found to be taking part in the *swadeshi* agitations their grant-in-aid would be cancelled. In a public meeting held on October 27, 1905 in central Calcutta, Rabindranath in his presidential address spoke against the circular, supported the students’ pledge to boycott the educational institutions and establishment of national education system for national consciousness.

Rabindranath pointed out the need for mass education for bridging the gulf between the educated elite and the masses. Instead of national education at the collegiate level, he thought that it would be wiser to concentrate on primary and secondary education with which should be combined training in useful crafts. Similar views of mass education were also forwarded by many contemporary intelligentsias. On November 4, 1905, a school was started for the rusticated students from Mufassil in the residence of Krishna Kumar Mitra (1852-1936), the editor of *Sanjibani*, a Bengali journal. Several zamindars / landlords and elite people like Subodh Chandra Mallik (1879-1920), Brajendra Kishore Roy Chowdhury, Zemindar of Gouripur, Mymensingh (1874-1957) and Maharaja Suryakanta Acharya Chowdhury of Muktagacha, Mymensingh (1851-1908) promised donation of huge sums for the establishment of a national university in Bengal. On November 5, 1905 Rabindranath lectured to a large gathering of students in a meeting held at the Dawn Society organized by Satishchandra Mukherjee (1865-1948). Again he stressed on national education for national consciousness. The National Education Movement progressed rapidly and the first National School was established at Rangpur on November 8, 1905 for imparting both general and technical education. The anti-Circular Society was established by the student leader Sachindraprasad Basu (? – 1941) in collaboration with Krishna Kumar Mitra and Ramkanta Roy.

R 4: What was Tagore’s vision of nationalism in the context of national education?

Rabindranath’s vision of nationalism was extended beyond the boundaries of the nation-state, embracing a broader concept of internationalism that emphasized cooperation and natural respect between different cultures and nations. He believed that true progress required a spirit of unity and understanding that transcended national boundaries. In essence Tagore’s nationalism was a call for a more humane and spiritual understanding of national identity that emphasized cooperation, understanding and the pursuit of shared human values. He saw the Western model of nationalism as a flawed and divisive force and he advocated for a more inclusive and harmonious vision of national unity.

Rabindranath was present in the Educational Conference of November 16, 1905 held at the Bengal Land-holders Association. The conference resolved to establish a National Council of Education – a system of education – literary, scientific and technical – on national lines under national control. Rabindranath was included as a member constituted for drawing up a provisional scheme of National Council of Education. The scheme was completed and considered in the second meeting of the conference held on December 10, 1905. A small Ways and means Committee was constituted to draw up a detailed report on the schemes and to fix course – curricula of the proposed National Education. Rabindranath (1861-1941), Taraknath Palit (1831-1914), Satish Chandra Mukherjee, Hirendranath Dutta (1868-1942), Narendranath Sen (1843 - 1911), Abdul Rassul (1874-1917), Subodh Chandra Mallik, Manamohon Bhattacharyya (?) and Dr. Nilratan Sircar (1861-1943) were appointed as members.

Rabindranath formulated a National Education scheme following the ancient ‘Tapaban’ model initiated in his Brahmyacharya Ashram at Santiniketan. In brief his proposals were:

1. National school should be residential so that the students and teachers would be in close contact with each other.
2. These schools should be established in the villages, that they would be self-sufficient, economically from the agricultural earnings of the land.
3. He recommended different course-curricula for boys and girls.
4. He strongly advocated the Upanishad based spiritual background in running the school.
5. Tagore advocated vernacular as the medium of instruction in all stages of education – primary to University levels. He advocated learning of European science and technology through the mother tongue.

The National Council of Bengal was formally constituted with 92 members including 6 Muslims covering a large number of Bengali intelligentsia along with Rabindranath. The National Council of Education gave affiliation to all National Schools of rural Bengal and established a school and a college in Calcutta, the Bengal National College and School which was inaugurated in a meeting held at Town Hall on August 14, 1906.

Tagore was the first to propose the concept of non-cooperation. By non-cooperation, he meant ‘non-requesting’ (begging) the British for reforms of rights, but starting earnestly to uplift the nation by Indians themselves. He wanted to build up a ‘Swadeshi Samaj’ as a policy of non-cooperation with the Government – a society which would function as ‘a State within a State’. Indian society was mostly village oriented, but the leaders were urban educated intelligentsias. To bridge this gap, he suggested organization of ‘Swadeshi Samaj’ on a vast scale.

In his presidential address at the Pabna Provincial Conference in 1908, he reiterated this and delivered his lecture in Bangla which caused a great stir among the English educated intelligentsia. Rabindranath along with some friends and relatives went ahead and organized a Swadeshi Samaj with some mottos, which were :—

1. We will educate our children in Swadeshi Schools as far as practicable.
2. We will buy our daily necessities from swadeshi stores.

In the inaugural ceremony of the Bengal National College and School Rabindranath was present reconciling his differences of opinions with most of the members of National Council of Education. He read his famous essay 'Jatiya Vidyalaya' (National School) in the meeting and hailed the National School as an achievement of the Bengalis, as an autonomous institution independent of Government's control and was the reflection of our 'Atma Shakti' (self-reliance). Rabindranath, however gradually became detached from the National Education Movement. In his political and educational thoughts, he sometimes did not agree with the moderates. The moderate approach of the ways and means was not acceptable to him. He wanted to do something 'new' following national tradition, as an alternative to English education provided by Indian universities. Later he remarked that those who had formal English education and became successful in life due to such education, they were unable to accept his new concept of education.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

In his letter to Ramendra Sundar Trivedi (1864-1919), he wrote – "I was not a leader or director in any association, but in any time country may again call me for working on National School then I would join it". Whenever required, Rabindranath cooperated with the National College and School which was evident from his participation in activities of the National Council of Education and the School. He delivered extension lecture to the students and teachers on Comparative Literature during 1906 – 1908. He was also appointed as a paper setter of Bengali for the Public Examination of the fifth and seventh standard conducted by the National Council of Education in 1906 and 1907. Even after this stint he continued his writings on education and some of the notables are: Tapabana (1909), Religious Instruction (1911), Education Act (1912) Goals and Education (1912), Female Education (1915) Medium of Instruction (1915), Controlling students (1915). In these articles and others, he relentlessly expressed his views on character, goal and methods of National Education, futility of English as the medium of instruction, necessity of education through mother tongue, defects of our instruction procedures, ideas of Santiniketan schools, female education and universal education. In his efforts to educational reform and development of rural societies he did not get much support from the contemporary intelligentsia.

REFERENCES

- Majumder, Nepal Chandra. (1929). *Bharate Jatiyota O Antarjatikata Ebong Rabindranath*. Vols. 1 & 2. Calcutta: Modern Book Agency Private LTD.
- Mukherjee, A. (1992). *Fifty years of National Education*. Calcutta : National Council of Bengal.
- Mukhopadhyay, P. K. (1992). *Rabindrajivani*. Vols.1- 3. Calcutta :Visva Bharati Granthan Bibhag.
- Sarkar, Prafulla Kumar. (1945). *Jatiya Andolane Rabindranath*. Calcutta : Hindusthan Prakasani.
- Sarkar, Sumit. (1973). *The Swadeshi Movement in Bengal (1903-1908)*. Calcutta : Peoples Publishing House.
- Sen, P. C. (1982). *Rabindranather Sikshachinta*. Calcutta : Paschim Banga Rajya Pustak Parshad.
- Trivedi, R. S. (1905). *Swadeshi Vidyalaya*, The Bangadarshan,1905.